

ISic3151

I.Sicily inscription 3151

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 916

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] Virius [---]

2. v(ir) s(pectabilis) [---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Virius, an admirable man.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493966

EDR 138383

EDCS 22200384

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a

l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 2004.0642

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 15

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3151. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357192>